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“BARE HANDS, FULL HEART”

It all started at a glance —
my eyes caught him out of nowhere,
something in him struck me still,
though unknown to me,
I was already the apple of his eyes.

My heart swelled full
as we held hands through the years —
and after six long seasons,
we tied the knot,
promising forever.

Then sweet turned to bitter,
finances grew uncertain,
hunger knocked at our door
life turned into haywire
yet I did not waver.

As the light of this family,
carried what needed carrying,
turning nothing on the table
into something to offer,
building a life from bare hands

bends the storm to her will,
harvest rain from drought, and
stitch sunrise from the dark
and a heart that refused to stop
the love that refuses to sit still